

Research Article

Digital Platform for Mental Health and Well-Being of University Students – A Case Study

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Abstract: University students often face significant mental health challenges, including stress, anxiety, depression, and academic burnout. However, many hesitate to seek help due to stigma, lack of awareness, or limited access to support services. Traditional mental health systems within universities are often fragmented, manual, and unable to meet rising demand efficiently. This project proposes a digital solution in the form of a mobile application developed using Microsoft Power Platform to enhance and streamline the delivery of mental health services for university students. The app consolidates key features such as psychological self-assessment tools, counselling session bookings, and access to mental health resources into a single, user-friendly platform. Data collected from user interactions are integrated with a Power BI dashboard, enabling mental health professionals to track trends, assess student needs, and make timely, data-driven decisions. By lowering the barriers to access and enabling early intervention, the app empowers students to take charge of their mental well-being. It also improves service efficiency for counselling teams by reducing administrative burdens. Designed with scalability in mind, this solution can be adapted by universities across different regions, offering a low-cost, low-code platform that integrates easily into existing institutional ecosystems. Beyond campus use, the solution has commercialization potential through partnerships with educational institutions, student wellness organizations, and government health initiatives. It aligns with the global push for digital health and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 3: Good Health and Well-being. Overall, this project demonstrates how digital innovation can make mental health support more accessible, proactive, and centered on students in higher education.

Keywords: Student wellness; Digital transformation; Mental health innovation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Mental health challenges among university students have been increasing, with studies showing that stress, anxiety, and depression significantly impact academic performance and well-being (Hunt & Eisenberg, 2010; Campbell et al., 2022). Counselling services play a crucial role in supporting students, but accessibility remains a major issue, as many hesitate to seek help due to stigma, lack of awareness, or logistical barriers (Gulliver et al., 2010). Digital solutions, particularly mobile applications, have emerged as effective approaches for increasing engagement in mental health services (Andersson et al., 2019; Philippe et al., 2022).

Microsoft Power Platform provides a low-code environment suitable for building integrated digital solutions in higher education (Microsoft, 2025; Microsoft Learn, 2025). This project utilizes the platform to develop a centralized mobile application that streamlines counselling services through features such as self-assessments, appointment scheduling, and mental health resources. Built with Power Apps, Power Automate, Power BI, and SharePoint Lists, the system ensures institutional integration and cost-effectiveness. This paper examines the platform's impact on student engagement and explores its potential for scalable implementation across higher education settings.

1.1 Background

Mental health issues among university students have become increasingly prevalent in recent years. Academic pressures, social transitions, and personal challenges contribute to high rates of stress, anxiety, and depression. However, many students do not seek professional help due to stigma, lack of awareness, or limited access to support services. Traditional campus-based mental health services often struggle with manual workflows, high demand, and fragmented delivery. In response, digital solutions—particularly mobile platforms—are gaining traction for their ability to improve accessibility, encourage early intervention, and provide scalable support. This study builds on that trend by exploring how a digital platform can be used to enhance mental health services in a higher education context.

1.2 Problem Statement

Despite the growing awareness of student mental health, many higher education institutions face challenges in delivering effective psychological support. Existing systems are often not equipped to handle increasing demand, resulting in long wait times and administrative inefficiencies. Additionally, students may be reluctant to seek help through traditional channels due to confidentiality concerns or stigma. The lack of integrated, data-driven systems further limits the ability of counselling teams to respond proactively to student needs. These limitations highlight the need for a centralized, user-friendly platform that supports both students and mental health professionals through improved accessibility, service coordination, and data utilization.

1.3 Research Objectives

This study aims to address the gaps in existing student mental health support systems through the following objectives:

- To reduce access barriers through digital tools.
- To encourage early intervention via self-assessment features.
- To support institutional counselling teams by streamlining workflows.
- To improve the quality of mental health care provided to students.

1.4 Literature Review

To contextualize the significance and uniqueness of the developed platform, a comparison was conducted with several existing mobile applications that aim to support student mental health. These systems vary in terms of target audience, features, and level of integration with institutional support services. The table below summarizes the key similarities and differences between the developed platform and other notable applications, highlighting the value of a university-specific, institutionally integrated solution.

Table 1. Comparison to other existing systems in the market

Feature / Aspect	Proposed Application	Moodschool	Smart Appointment System (SAS)	AI-Based Therapy Apps
Target Users	University students	General college students	University students	General users with anxiety/depression
Integration with Institution	Integrated with university’s counselling system	Standalone platform	Limited – student-teacher appointment system	Not tied to any institution
Appointment Booking	Booking with real counsellors in the institution	Not included	Booking with counsellors	Not included
Self-Assessment Tools	Includes DASS-21, PHQ-9, WHODAS 2.0, CBI	Limited	Not included	Some include symptom checkers
Mental Health Resources	Tailored to university student needs	General resources	Limited	Self-guided programs
AI or Chatbot Features	No	No	No	Yes
Data Analytics & Monitoring	Yes	No	No	Limited
Data Storage & Privacy	Secured under institutional control	Not specified	Not clearly defined	Varies by app
Customization for Institution	Built for specific institutional needs with input from students and staff	No	Partially customizable	No

The comparison highlights that while many existing mental health applications provide valuable features such as general self-help resources, AI-driven support, and appointment systems, they often lack deep integration with institutional counselling services. In contrast, the developed platform distinguishes itself by aligning closely with the needs of a specific university environment. Its integration with existing workflows, personalized assessment tools, and institutional dashboards ensures both students and counsellors benefit from a more seamless and context-aware experience. This tailored approach enhances trust, encourages student engagement, and allows for more accurate monitoring and support within the higher education setting.

1.5 Case Study

This project was implemented at a private university in Malaysia known for its strong academic focus in engineering, science, and technology. The university emphasizes innovation, research, and student-centered development, making it a suitable environment for digital transformation initiatives in education and student support services.

The university has integrated Microsoft Power Platform and other cloud-based tools across various operations, including teaching, learning, and administration. This case study demonstrates how digital tools can enhance the delivery of mental health services within a higher education ecosystem, aligning with the institution’s broader digitalization efforts to support student well-being and institutional efficiency.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study followed a structured software development approach to ensure that the proposed digital solution aligns with both user needs and technical feasibility (Pressman & Maxim, 2020). The project was conducted through several phases: Initialization, Planning and Design, Requirement Gathering, Development, Verification, and Deployment.

Figure 1. Flowchart of project development

Figure 1 presents the overall development methodology adopted for this project. Each phase was structured to ensure alignment with the project’s objectives, beginning with early-stage interviews and ending with user testing and refinement. This systematic approach allowed for continuous stakeholder involvement, iterative improvements, and effective integration of both user and technical requirements throughout the development lifecycle.

2.1 Research Design (Initialization)

A qualitative research approach was adopted to explore the perspectives of both mental health service providers and students. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with counsellors and students who regularly interacted with mental health services at a higher institution. These interviews aimed to identify limitations in current systems and opportunities for improvement (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Development followed an Agile Iterative methodology to enable continuous feedback and refinement (Beck et al., 2001).

2.2 Data Collection (Requirements Gathering)

Primary data were gathered through qualitative methods designed to capture insights from both mental health service providers and students. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with counsellors to explore administrative workflows, service delivery challenges, and opportunities for digital integration. Concurrently, interviews with students were held to identify common mental health concerns and preferences for digital support features. Additionally, user testing sessions were conducted to evaluate the platform’s usability, functionality, and overall user satisfaction, allowing for iterative improvements based on real-world feedback. Secondary data sources included existing literature on digital mental health interventions, counselling practices, and documentation related to Microsoft Power Platform tools (Andersson et al., 2019; Microsoft, 2025).

2.3 Planning

During the planning phase, it was decided that the application would be developed using Microsoft Power Platform to ensure smooth integration, low-code development, and easy maintenance. Power Apps was chosen to build the mobile interface so that both students and counsellors could use it easily. SharePoint Lists were used as the backend to manage student data, mental health assessments, and counselling bookings. Power Automate was selected to automate tasks like sending notifications and processing forms. Power BI was included to help counsellors view trends and patterns in student mental health, making it easier for them to make informed decisions. This planning phase helped define the main features and tools needed to meet the project’s goals.

2.4 System Design (Design, Implementation)

The platform is designed to support two primary user groups: students and counsellors. Students have access to key functionalities such as scheduling counselling sessions, completing psychological self-assessments, and exploring a curated repository of mental health resources. The assessments included are DASS-21, WHODAS 2.0, PHQ-9, and the Copenhagen Burnout Inventory (CBI), all of which are widely used in clinical and academic settings, including by professionals within the Ministry of Health Malaysia (KKM) and university counselling centres. Counsellors are provided with tools to monitor student engagement, review assessment results, and manage appointments through an integrated Power BI dashboard that offers real-time insights into student well-being trends.

Figure 2. Screenshots of the mobile application interface: (a) Self-assessment tools, (b) Appointment booking page, (c) Mental health resources

As illustrated in Figure 2, the mobile application features an intuitive interface designed to support students in managing their mental health. The platform includes several key functionalities, beginning with psychological self-assessment tools such as DASS-21, WHODAS 2.0, PHQ-9, and the Copenhagen Burnout Inventory (CBI), which enable students to evaluate their mental well-being independently. It also offers a convenient appointment booking system, allowing students to schedule counselling sessions directly through the app. Additionally, the application provides access to a curated collection of mental health resources, including educational content and self-help materials relevant to common student concerns.

Figure 3. Power BI dashboard of the application

On the counsellor side, an integrated Power BI dashboard displays student engagement data, assessment results, and appointment activity, supporting timely interventions and data-driven service delivery. These features collectively enhance the accessibility, efficiency, and effectiveness of mental health support in higher education settings.

3. FINDINGS

To assess the platform’s usability, functionality, and relevance, user testing was conducted from late February to early March 2025. The testing process involved two main stakeholder groups: mental health service providers, consisting of one counsellor and one manager, and ten university students who regularly interacted with counselling services. This phase aimed to gather direct feedback on the platform’s core features and identify areas for refinement.

Student participants generally reported a positive experience with the platform. They found the interface easy to navigate and appreciated the intuitive layout of the application. The inclusion of psychological self-assessments such as DASS-21 and PHQ-9, along with access to mental health resources, was noted as particularly helpful. Students also provided constructive feedback, suggesting the implementation of push notifications to alert them of appointment confirmations and the addition of a feature to delete messages in the chat module.

From the perspective of the counsellors, the platform significantly improved administrative efficiency. The automated appointment scheduling system and integration with Power BI enabled easier tracking of student engagement and better visualization of assessment data. This reduced the reliance on manual processes and enhanced the ability to monitor student well-being trends over time. Counsellors also emphasized the importance of ensuring scalability and long-term data management as the platform grows.

Figure 4. Push notification function implemented in the mobile application

In response to the feedback received, two improvements were implemented: the introduction of push notifications and a message deletion feature within the chat interface. These enhancements addressed user concerns and contributed to greater satisfaction among both students and staff.

4. DISCUSSION

The development and pilot testing of the proposed digital platform demonstrated significant improvements in the accessibility and efficiency of mental health service delivery within a higher institution. By consolidating appointment scheduling, psychological self-assessment tools, and mental health resources into a single application, the platform addressed common barriers students face in seeking support—such as time constraints, lack of awareness, and perceived stigma (Gulliver et al., 2010; Campbell et al., 2022).

User testing showed that students valued the platform's simplicity and accessibility. Counsellors found it easier to manage appointments and interpret assessment data for early intervention. The addition of features such as push notifications and chat message deletion highlighted the value of incorporating user feedback during development. However, some features, such as appointment rescheduling, were not implemented due to operational concerns. This decision reflects the importance of balancing student flexibility with administrative feasibility.

Despite its strengths, the platform's deployment was limited to a small group due to institutional approval constraints. Future collaboration with relevant administrative departments will be necessary to facilitate full-scale implementation and integration into official systems.

4.1 Future Works

While the platform has successfully met its initial objectives, several enhancements are planned to extend its functionality and broaden its impact. One of the key future developments includes the integration of an AI-powered chatbot to provide real-time responses to frequently asked questions, guide students to appropriate mental health resources, and deliver preliminary support before engagement with counsellors. This feature aims to enhance user experience while reducing the administrative burden on counselling staff.

In addition, the platform will be enhanced with customizable features that allow students to set personal well-being goals, monitor their assessment history, and track mental health progress over time. These tools are intended to empower users and encourage sustained, self-guided engagement.

Plans are also in place for a full-scale rollout across the institution, followed by expansion into other higher education environments. Future versions of the platform will explore multilingual and cross-campus support to improve accessibility and inclusivity. Lastly, the project team intends to pursue strategic partnerships with ministries, NGOs, and private universities to ensure the platform's long-term growth, sustainability, and relevance across a broader educational and mental health landscape.

5. CONCLUSION

This project presented a low-code, scalable digital platform aimed at improving the delivery of mental health services for students in higher institutions. The application successfully centralized core counselling services into a single, user-friendly solution. It demonstrated that digitizing support processes can enhance both student engagement and counsellor efficiency.

The pilot deployment showed promising outcomes, with positive feedback from both students and mental health staff. Features such as self-assessment tracking, appointment automation, and data-driven insights proved effective in addressing key challenges faced by traditional service models.

While full institutional rollout remains a future goal, the system's architecture and development approach offer a replicable framework for other higher institutions seeking to modernize their mental health services. Further enhancements could strengthen the platform's capacity to support student well-being on a larger scale. With proper institutional support and continued user-centered development, this platform has the potential to play a vital role in supporting mental health and well-being across higher education settings.

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References

- Badesha, K., Wilde, S., & Dawson, D. L. (2022). Mental health mobile application use to manage psychological difficulties: An umbrella review. *Mental Health Review Journal*, 27(3), 241–280. <https://doi.org/10.1108/mhrj-02-2021-0014>
- Campbell, F., Blank, L., Cantrell, A., Baxter, S., Blackmore, C., Dixon, J., & Goyder, E. (2022). Factors that influence mental health of university and college students in the UK: A systematic review. *BMC Public Health*, 22(1), Article 13943. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-13943-x>
- Chen, B., Yang, T., Xiao, L., Xu, C., & Zhu, C. (2022). Effects of mobile mindfulness meditation on the mental health of university students: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 25, e39128. <https://doi.org/10.2196/39128>
- Dalvi, A., Kapur, P., Ashtekar, R., Gorugantu, A., & Siddavatham, I. (2023). Transforming college counseling: An in-house solution for student mental wellness. *Proceedings of the 2023 2nd International Conference for Innovation in Technology (INOCON)*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/inocon57975.2023.10101364>
- Diano, F., Sica, L. S., & Ponticorvo, M. (2023). A systematic review of mobile apps as an adjunct to psychological interventions for emotion dysregulation. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(2), 1431. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20021431>
- Hayoung Bae, B. (2023, November 20). Application-based interventions for moderate to severe depression. *JAMA Network Open*. <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jamanetworkopen/fullarticle/2812076>
- Islam, M. K., Boshra, S. J., Rahman, M., Jony, M. M. I., & Rahat, I. A. (2023). Android-based smart appointment system (SAS) for booking and interacting with teacher for counselling. *Proceedings of the 2021 International Conference on Emerging Smart Computing and Informatics (ESCI)*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/esci56872.2023.10099495>
- King's College London. (2023, September 28). Student mental health problems have almost tripled, study finds. *King's College London*. <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/news/student-mental-health-problems-have-almost-tripled-study-finds>
- LaMontagne, L. G., Doty, J. L., Diehl, D. C., Nesbit, T. S., Gage, N. A., Kumbkarni, N. K., & Leon, S. P. (2023). Acceptability, usage, and efficacy of mindfulness apps for college student mental health: A systematic review and meta-analysis of RCTs. *Journal of Affective Disorders*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0165032724014939>

- Linardon, J., Fuller-Tyszkiewicz, M., Firth, J., Goldberg, S. B., Anderson, C., McClure, Z., & Torous, J. (2024). Systematic review and meta-analysis of adverse events in clinical trials of mental health apps. *npj Digital Medicine*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01388-y>
- Liu, X., Guo, Y., Zhang, W., & Gao, W. (2022). Influencing factors, prediction, and prevention of depression in college students: A literature review. *World Journal of Psychiatry*, 12(7), 860–873. <https://doi.org/10.5498/wjp.v12.i7.860>
- Mental Illness and Addiction: Facts and Statistics. (2025). *Centre for Addiction and Mental Health (CAMH)*. <https://www.camh.ca/en/driving-change/the-crisis-is-real/mental-health-statistics>
- Microsoft Power Apps – Build apps with AI. (2025). *Microsoft*. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-my/power-platform/products/power-apps/>
- O’Leary, T., & Torous, J. (2022). Smartphone apps for eating disorders: An overview of the marketplace and research trends. *International Journal of Eating Disorders*, 55(5), 625–632. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eat.23690>
- Philippe, T. J., Sikder, N., Jackson, A., Koblanski, M. E., Liow, E., Pilarinos, A., & Vasarhelyi, K. (2022). Digital health interventions for delivery of mental health care: Systematic and comprehensive meta-review. *JMIR Mental Health*, 9(5), e35159. <https://doi.org/10.2196/35159>
- Power Apps pricing. (2025). *Microsoft Power Platform*. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/power-platform/products/power-apps/pricing/>
- Tapanm-Msft. (2025). Official Microsoft Power Apps documentation – Power Apps. *Microsoft Learn*. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/power-apps/>